

STUDY ON FRICTION PERFORMANCE OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITE UNDER LUBRICATION CONDITION

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SUMMARY

Carbon/carbon composite is an environment-friendly material. A kind of carbon/carbon composite reinforced by 1K carbon cloth was produced through isothermal CVI method. After property tests under lubrication condition, the results showed that it was of excellent friction performance and did little harm to its mating plate.

Keywords: Carbon/carbon composite; lubrication; isothermal CVI; friction and wear

1 Introduction

Due to the high ratio of strength-to-density, modulus-to-density, excellent friction properties and shock resistance at elevated temperature, carbon/carbon composites play more and more important roles not only in military fields, but also for civil applications [1-4].

Carbon/carbon composites were introduced in aircrafts as brake discs and pads since 1973. Later they were introduced in racing cars and motorcycles in the 1980s [5, 6]. However, in previous studies, most of the work were focused on their application under dry conditions. In this paper, friction and wear performance under lubrication conditions for 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon composite were studied. The morphology of the carbon/carbon composites after friction test was characterised by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

1K carbon cloth used as deposition matrix was provided by Jilin Carbon Group,

China.. K300 carbon fiber with a density of 0.5 g/cm^3 applied for linking carbon cloth was purchased from Tory Group, Japan. The propylene with a purity of 99.5% was used directly without further purification..

2.2 Sample Preparation

An annulus laminated preform with a size of (OD) 128 mm \times (ID) 99 mm was fixed in a graphite holder, infiltrated at 900-1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ by ICVI process, taking propylene as the precursor and nitrogen as the diluted gas. Then the as-infiltrated carbon/carbon composite material was graphitized. The sample density was measured as 1.65 g/cm^3 .

As shown in Figure 1, sample of carbon cloth reinforcing carbon composite was processed into a shape of annulus one It was pasted onto the testing machine disk, with evenly distributed oil grooves on the surface. The surface of the sample was grinded and cleaned with acetone. It was then immersed into No. N32 engine oil.

Fig.1 Sample of friction material and its grooves

2.3 Measurements

The friction and wear performance tests were conducted on a QM1000-II wet friction tester. The main parameters were set as: braking pressure, 0-2.0 MPa; rotating speed, 1000-4000rpm. The separator plate was made of No.45 steel (carbon content: 45wt%) with a mean surface roughness of Ra 0.32 μm . and hardness of HRC 35. No. N32 engine oil (kinematic viscosity is 28.8-35.2 mm²/s at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) was used in all friction tests. The inertia was 0.1Kg·m². Figure 2 is a simplified sketch of the equipment [7].

When the ac motor came to the setting speed, a normal force was applied to the separator by a hydraulic cylinder, and it needed about 0.2 s to reach steady pressure. The friction torque was measured by a torque transducer and was transmitted to a computer. In the meantime, the torque curve was recorded and the friction coefficient was calculated by a computer.

Thermocouples of type *K* were embedded into the separator plate to measure the temperature of the separator plate and were installed in the oil tank to measure the temperature of the oil.

Fig.2 Schematic diagram of QM1000- II B wet friction performance tester

1. flywheel 2. speed recorder 3. clutch 4. guide for friction plate 5. sample 6. separator plate
7. hydraulic cylinder 8. flowmeter 9. oil tank 10. ac motor 11. pyrogenation installation
12. thermometer 13. computer 14. controller 15. ac motor 16 frequency drum

In order to establish nearly complete contact with the separator plate and get the steady μ_d , the friction couple was subjected to a run-in for about 120 min (once every 1 min) at the braking pressure of 0.25 MPa and the rotating speed of 950 rpm, respectively.

The friction torque curves under different operating conditions were recorded by a computer. The μ_d , a mean value of the coefficient from the sliding part of the engagement, was calculated from the equation as follows:

$$\mu_d = \frac{3M(R_0^2 - R_i^2)}{2P(R_0^3 - R_i^3)}$$

Where M is the friction torque, R_0 is the half outer diameter of the sample, R_i is the half inner diameter of the sample, and P is the axial force on the clutch plates.

According to actual operating conditions, the ranges of braking pressure, rotating speed, oil temperature, and oil flow rate were 0.3-2.0 MPa, 1000-4000 rpm, 50-120 °C, and 8-250 ml/min, respectively.

The sample's surface after friction tests was characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL 6460).

3 Results and Discussion

The rotating speed, braking pressure are important factors that contributes to the friction performance of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon/carbon composites. In this

work, the nature of the effects of braking pressure, rotating speed and inertia of main shaft on friction properties were studied.

3.1 Characterization of Friction Coefficient

3.1.1 Dynamic Friction Coefficient

Figure 3 shows the friction curves of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon/carbon composite material under braking speeds of 1000, 2000, 3000 and 4000 rpm. The tester recorded the braking pressure in the range between 0 and 2.0 Mpa with the inertia of

Fig. 3 Dynamic friction coefficient of C/C reinforced by 1K carbon fiber as a function of braking pressure

Fig. 4 Static / Dynamic friction coefficient of C/C reinforced by 1K carbon fiber as a function of braking pressure

main shaft as $0.1 \text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$. The dynamic friction coefficient gradually decreases with braking pressure. However there is a big drop for samples under 1000 rpm braking speed which implying there is an incomplete contact between friction plate and corresponding disk, therefore generating the low braking pressure.

Figure 4 showed the dynamic (μ_d) and static (μ_s) friction coefficient for samples particularly under 2000 rpm and main shaft at $0.1 \text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$. There is a decrease in the ratio

Fig. 5 Dynamic friction coefficient of C/C reinforced by 1K carbon cloth as a function of inertia in different braking pressure

Fig. 6 Dynamic friction coefficient of C/C reinforced by 1K carbon cloth as a function of pressure in different inertia

(μ_d/μ_s), suggesting weaker friction stability with increasing braking pressure. The decreasing rate of dynamic friction coefficient being higher than that of static coefficient once the pressure exceeds 0.8 MPa.

Figure 5 shows the dynamic friction coefficients of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon/carbon composites at different braking pressures and a velocity of 2000 r/min. In this figure, μ_d has a greatest change when braking pressure 0.5 MPa. Additionally, when braking pressure equals a small value, the maximum of μ_d lies on the point of a large main shaft inertia, while the maximum of μ_d transfers to a point of a relatively small main shaft inertia with the increase of braking pressure.

Fig. 6 shows the dynamic friction coefficient of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon/carbon composites at different inertias and the velocity of 2000 r/min. Dynamic friction coefficient reaches a peak when the inertia is 0.4 Kg·m², while it has a relatively small value when the values of main shaft inertia is equal to 0.2 Kg·m² and 0.6 Kg·m². Moreover, all dynamic friction coefficients increases at the first time and decreases with the increase of braking pressure.

Fig. 7 Static friction coefficient of C/C reinforced by 1K carbon cloth as a function of Inertia in different inertia

Fig. 8 Static friction coefficient of C/C reinforced by 1K carbon cloth as a function of inertia in different braking pressure

3.1.2 Static Friction Coefficient

Figure 7 shows the static friction coefficient of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon/carbon composites under varying main shaft inertias with the changes of braking pressure and a velocity of 2000 r/min. It is revealed that the inertia of main shaft has a greater influence in particularly on samples under lower braking pressure. Moreover, braking pressure does little influence on static coefficient when inertia extends from 0.2 to 0.3 Kg·m².

Figure 8 shows the static friction coefficient of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon/carbon composites with the changes of inertia. It is likely that when braking pressure equals small values, μ_s increases with the increase of inertias of main shaft, while μ_s declines with the rising braking pressure. However, when braking pressure exceeds 1.5 MPa, μ_s keeps stable. All phenomena above indicate a more stable braking

process when taking engagements between friction plate and its corresponding plate.

3.2 Characterization of Wear Performance

The wear rate has proven an important parameter of assessing the friction performance [8-11]. It has been known that there are many factors could affect wear rate, i.e. corresponding plate and oil flow rate. In this paper, wear rate under repeated cycles was investigated while keeping braking pressure, rotating speed, oil temperature, and oil flow rate of 0.5 MPa, 2000 rpm, 70 °C-75 °C and 90 ml/min, respectively. The wear rate was calculated as $6.00 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3/\text{J}$ eventually.

Fig. 9 SEM of carbon/carbon composite reinforced by 1K carbon cloth

The SEM micrograph of sample after wear testing is shown in Figure 9. It is observed that sample surface is partly polished, with some abrasive dust on the top. A layer of transfer film is formed and it is speculated as the main contribution to the stable friction performance.

4 Conclusions

A kind of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing carbon/carbon composite material was prepared in this paper and its friction and wear performance and morphology were investigated. Conclusions could be drawn as follows:

1. Friction performance of 1K carbon cloth reinforcing C/C composite material are affected by the following key factors: braking pressure, main shaft inertia and rotating speed.

2. Both dynamic and static friction coefficient decrease with the increase of the braking pressure. μ_d changes most with the increase of inertia when the inertia equals 0.5 MPa.

3. The sample wear rate is measured as $6.00 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3/\text{J}$, SEM results indicates that a layer of transfer film has been formed.

5 Reference

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